

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation of Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable D 8.3

Final public event

Project acronym:	OPEUS
Starting date:	01/11/2016
Duration (in months):	36
Call (part) identifier:	H2020-S2R-OC-CCA-2015-02
Grant agreement no:	730827
Due date of deliverable:	Month 36 – 31 October 2019
Actual submission date:	20/11/2019
Responsible/Author:	Christine HASSOUN, UIC
Dissemination level:	PU
Status:	Final

Reviewed: (yes)

Document history		
<i>Revision</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	28/10/2019	First issue by UIC
2	31/10/2019	Review by Newcastle University
3	17/11/2019	Review by UITP
4	18/11/2019	Review by University of Rostock
5	19/11/2019	Final draft issued

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D8.3 is a detailed report on the joint Shift2Rail CCA OPEUS and FINE1 final event that was held at UIC in Paris on October 17th, 2019.

This report describes all the actions undertaken by the project partners to organise the OPEUS final event. Among others, it contains:

- The agenda of the event;
- A description of the attendance;
- The dissemination material (publication of news, update of the website, intensive use of twitter, etc.);
- The publication of the presentation delivered during the conference;
- The highlights of the conference from OPEUS point of view.

All project partners collaborated in the success of this event which was an excellent opportunity to further disseminate the project results and to reinforce the link with our complementary Shift2Rail (S2R) project FINE1.

The event attendees also benefited from the participation of the S2R DESTINATE project (dedicated to railway noise abatement measures), as their Project Coordinator presented the key results of their project which had completed in October 2018.

2. Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronyms	Description
CCA	Cross Cutting Activities
DESTINATE	S2R project - “Decision supporting tools for implementation of cost-efficient railway noise abatement measures”
FINE1	S2R project – “Future Improvement for Energy and Noise”
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Innovation Programme
OPEUS	S2R Project – “Modelling and strategies for the assessment and Optimisation of Energy Usage aspects of rail innovation”
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
UIC	Union Internationale des Chemins de fer
UITP	Union Internationale des Transports Publics
WP	Work Package

3. Background

Within the scope of the OPEUS project, the focus of Work Package 8 (WP8) is “Engagement”. Its objective is “to establish a clear and fruitful communication platform between the OPEUS activities and those outside the consortium focusing in particular on the essential relationship with the Shift2Rail (S2R) founding members and associates and their innovation activities related to OPEUS”.

WP8 runs throughout the project’s 36-month duration. During its timeline, particular emphasis has been placed on coordinating the activities of OPEUS with those of other relevant S2R projects and activities, primarily FINE1 (“Future Improvement for Energy and Noise”). Dialogue between the two projects has been maintained in various formats so as to enable the regular interchange of information and experiences between the two projects. These have included telephone, email, face-to-face meetings and the exchange of ‘twinned’ deliverable reports. From the outset, each project had planned for an ‘open’ final event to take place, and it was considered during the projects’ lifetimes that a joint effort would enable the strongest potential by which to communicate and disseminate both projects’ results and impacts.

This document constitutes the Deliverable D8.3 “Final public event” in the framework of the WP8 Engagement of OPEUS project (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015). It contributes to task 8.1 (Communication Platform) and task 8.2 (Advisory Board).

4. Objective/Aim

One of the important tasks of WP8-engagement, was the organisation of a final event to disseminate the project results of the S2R OPEUS project “Modelling and strategies for the assessment and OPTimisation of Energy USage aspects of rail innovation”.

To maximise the attendance and ensure the continuity between Shift2Rail funded JU projects, it was decided to organise the final event jointly with the complementary project FINE1 “Future Improvement for Energy and Noise” and to invite the coordinator of the S2R DESTINATE project “Decision supporting tools for implementation of cost-efficient railway noise abatement measures” to also present the key results of this project which ended in October 2018 and dedicated on noise.

5. Organisation of the event

This event was organised jointly with the Shift2Rail JU CCA complementary project FINE1. It was held at UIC in Paris on October 17th, 2019.

Contacts were established in May 2019 between the OPEUS and FINE1 project partners to decide the date and place of the conference.

The save the date was released early (beginning of June 2019). Practical details were discussed rapidly afterwards and there were several iterations of the carefully constructed agenda developed between OPEUS and FINE1, so as to ensure the maximum and most appropriate content. A draft programme was released in July, early enough to ensure the maximum participation possible. The definite programme was published in the first days of October.

Partners of both projects used their own channels to advertise the event largely on social media and by emailing.

5.1. Agenda of the event

As OPEUS and FINE1 covered two different topics, the event was organised in two separate rooms.

All participants were at first invited to attend the joint high-level session organised in the largest room. This session was dedicated to the presentation of:

- FINE1 project
- OPEUS project
- DESTINATE project, and
- To present the Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking and discuss the future challenges for the sector in liaison with the topics of these projects, i.e. energy and noise.

The audience was then split into both rooms:

- First one gathering OPEUS and several FINE1 partners dedicated to **energy**;
- Second one with only FINE1 partners dedicated to **noise**.

To enable efficient networking between the participants of the 2 sessions, a lunch and 2 coffee breaks were organised during the day.

A detailed agenda with all the speaker biographies was prepared, printed and distributed to all participants to the conference (see annex 1).

9:30 -10:30: Registration and welcome coffee	
10:30-11:30: Joint high-level session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FINE1 Coordinator – Haike Brick • OPEUS Coordinator – Roberto Palacin • DESTINATE Coordinator – Jenny Böhm • S2R JU Representative – Judit Sandor • DG RTD Representative – William Bird
FINE1 session on 'Noise'	FINE1 & OPEUS joint session on 'Energy'
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 11:30-11:45: Introduction of the FINE1 Noise & Vibration sub-project <i>(Haike Brick, Bombardier Transportation)</i> ▪ 11:45-12:30: Auralisation & Visualisation <i>(Rüdiger Garburg, Deutsche Bahn; Jenny Böhm, TU Berlin)</i> 	<p>Cluster 1: Introduction and case studies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 11:30-11:40: Introduction of the FINE1 Energy sub-project <i>(Henry Völker, Bombardier Transportation)</i> ▪ 11:40-11:50: OPEUS Tool – a look inside <i>(Lukas Pröhl, University of Rostock)</i> ▪ 11:50-12:05: Energy case study 1 - Simulation of hybrid electric trains using OPEUS tool <i>(Tony Letrouvé, SNCF; Dinh An Nguyen, SAFT)</i> ▪ 12:05-12:20: Energy case study 2 – Traction energy losses analysis <i>(Maria Marsilla, Stadler)</i> ▪ 12:20-12:30: Facilitated discussion, Q&A
12:30-13:30: Lunch	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 13:30-13:50: Technical assessment and integration of N&V tasks on system level <i>(Dennis Fast, Bombardier Transportation)</i> ▪ 13:50-14:10: Traffic noise scenarios and baseline for evaluation and monitoring of noise effects in S2R innovations <i>(Philipp Geiger, Deutsche Bahn; Rüdiger Garburg, Deutsche Bahn)</i> ▪ 14:10-14:30: Interior noise modelling <i>(Torsten Kohrs, Bombardier Transportation)</i> ▪ 14:30-14:50: Specification & characterisation of acoustic sources & assemblies <i>(Nezam Sanei, Alstom)</i> ▪ 14:50-15:10: Presentation of the DESTINATE project <i>(Jenny Böhm, TU Berlin)</i> ▪ 15:10-15:30: FINE2 outlook <i>(Rüdiger Garburg, Deutsche Bahn)</i> ▪ 15:30-16:00: Q&A 	<p>Cluster 2: Key results & recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 13:30-13:45: Shift2Rail Energy KPI results <i>(Holger Dittus, DLR)</i> ▪ 13:45-14:15: Energy Label & EN 50591 <i>(Henry Völker, Bombardier Transportation)</i> ▪ 14:15-14:30: EU energy-efficiency politics <i>(Samuel Hibon, Alstom; Michel Mermet-Guyennet, Alstom)</i> ▪ 14:30-14:45: OPEUS Position Paper <i>(Laurent Dauby, UITP)</i> ▪ 14:45-15:00: Facilitated discussion, Q&A <p>Cluster 3: What is next?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 15:10-15:25: FINE2 outlook <i>(Jürgen Ernst, Deutsche Bahn)</i> ▪ 15:25-15:40: OPEUS tool enhancement <i>(Lukas Pröhl, Rostock University; Harald Aschemann, Rostock University)</i> ▪ 15:40-16:00: Facilitated discussion, Q&A
16:00-17:00: Networking coffee	

5.2. Attendance in the conference

The OPEUS and FINE1 final event was attended by 70 participants from ten European countries (see list of attending companies and area of interest in annex 2 of this report). The targeted audience detailed in deliverable 8.1 was well represented with mostly members from the industry, the railway undertakings, the policy makers, railway associations and academia.

Figure 1 Group picture of the OPEUS and FINE1 Final event

5.3. Cooperation with other Shift2Rail JU projects

This event was organised jointly with the FINE1 project which enabled to maximise the attendance to the event and has ensured a large dissemination of the project results.

The presence of the coordinator of the DESTINATE project is another excellent sign of cooperation between Shift2Rail projects to work on the future of railways.

5.4. Dissemination material

The date and place and the agenda of the OPEUS and FINE1 final event was largely announced via:

- Four emails were sent to the Railway community (see in annex 3 copy of one of these emails);
- The OPEUS twitter account: Several tweets were posted from the OPEUS twitter account to communicate the date and place of the conference and to share the updates on the agenda. The effect of the OPEUS twitter account was demultiplied by the retweets made by the S2R JU, and by the project partners which have a large number of followers in the railway domain and beyond.

Figure 2 Image of an announcement tweet

- The OPEUS website: a news was published on the OPEUS website to communicate the date and place of the conference and to share the updates on the agenda (<http://opeus-project.eu/>, tab news and event – see copy of the news in annex 4 of this report).
- The UIC e-News: the date, place and agenda of the final event were announced several times on the UIC e-news:
 - FINE 1 & OPEUS Final Conference to be held on 17 October 2019 at UIC Paris headquarters, UIC e-News #656 of 23/07/2019 (<https://uic.org/com/uic-e-news/656/>);
 - FINE 1 & OPEUS Final Conference to be held on 17 October 2019 at UIC Paris headquarters, UIC e-News #657 of 30/07/2019 (<https://uic.org/com/uic-e-news/657/>);
 - FINE 1 & OPEUS Final Conference to be held on 17 October 2019 at UIC Paris headquarters, UIC e-News #658 of 03/09/2019 (<https://uic.org/com/uic-e-news/658/>);
- The UIC website: A banner was placed in June 2019 on the UIC website to announce the date and place of the final event. This banner was linked to the registration form of the event and to the updated agenda.

Figure 3 Banner on the UIC website

5.5. Actions after the conference

Presentations made during the joint high-level session and the energy session are all available for download on the OPEUS website (<http://opeus-project.eu/>, tab downloads).

They are sorted by cluster as they were presented, i.e.:

- Cluster 1: Case studies
- Cluster 2: Key results and recommendations
- Cluster 3: What is Next

Below an image of the organisation of the presentations to be downloaded as they appear on the OPEUS website.

Figure 4 Delivered presentations on the OPEUS website

Participants were informed by mail and by twitter after the conference that all OPEUS presentations are available for download. Below a copy of the tweet posted after the conference.

Figure 5 Tweet to download presentation on the OPEUS website

An article to summarise the content of the final conference was published in the UIC e-News #666 of 29 October 2019 (<https://uic.org/com/uic-e-news/666/>) and in the OPEUS website.

5.6. OPEUS highlights during the final event

The key message of the OPEUS partners on this event was as follows:

- OPEUS has been successful in developing a tool able to assess the energy usage implications of introducing technological innovation in rolling stock, with particular emphasis on case studies related to energy storage systems, traction chain losses and quantifying the benefits of solutions being developed by the S2R IPs;
- The developed OPEUS-Tool is already utilized (or a utilization is scheduled) by some Shift2Rail partners for both internal investigations as well as for following Shift2Rail projects (e.g. FINE1, FINE2).
- In the scope of 'Cluster 3: What is next?' a possible enhancement of the OPEUS-Tool was presented. This outlook includes further developments in two main fields:
 - Distribution, Handling, Publication of the tool - Covering the development of the graphical user interface as well as possibilities for a simpler use of the tool.
 - Extension of the functionalities of the tool – Consideration of a wide scope of possible enhancements to add further capability to improve scope and accuracy e.g. machine learning algorithms for energy optimized operating strategies, assessment of thermal aspects, extension of the model topologies (e.g. include fuel cells) as well as extensions to cover further infrastructure parameters.

- The presented possibilities for the enhancement were discussed afterwards, which results in further enhancement suggestions, e.g. an inclusion of a detailed HVAC (heating-ventilation-air-conditioning) model.
- A draft position paper on the energy outlook for railway systems was presented covering areas such as potential actions underpinned by the Avoid-shift-improve approach, contribution of the work of OPEUS to the objectives of S2R and a set of recommendations to support addressing energy related aspects of railway systems. These can be summarised as the need to have a holistic approach to energy efficiency will deliver substantial benefits towards decarbonisation. The position paper, in this sense, turned out to be aligned with EC policy towards decarbonisation and climate change actions.

6. Conclusions

The joint OPEUS and FINE1 final event was organised at UIC in Paris on 17 October 2019. 70 participants from ten European countries attended the event. Participants came mostly from the industry, the railway undertakings, the policy makers, railway associations and academia which were the primary targets of the project since inception.

Several means of dissemination were used to ensure as many participants as possible. The event was largely announced via:

- Emails sent to the railway community
- The UIC e-News
- The UIC website
- The OPEUS website
- Twitter

The joint organisation of this event enabled the OPEUS project partners to maximise the attendance to the event and ensured a large dissemination of the project results in the railway community.

The organisation of the event was a carefully planned process to ensure a successful event with an enriching technical content.

The day offered ample time to discuss the key message of the OPEUS project and the future of railways in the two project topics, i.e. noise and energy.

7. Annexes

7.1. Printed agenda

We have the pleasure to invite you to

Final Conference
of the Shift2Rail JU Funded
CCA Projects

FINE1 and OPEUS

Detailed Programme
FINE1 & OPEUS Final Conference

17 October 2019
iUTP Examen Centre
16 rue Jean Rey, 75015 Paris, France

13:30-13:30: Registration and welcome coffee

13:30-11:30: Joint high-level session

- FINE1 Coordinator - Holke Brick
- OPEUS Coordinator - Roberto Palacin
- DESTINATE Coordinator - Jenny Böhm
- Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking Representatives - Judith Sander
- DG RTD Representative - William Bird

13:30-12:30: Parallel Sessions

13:30-14:00: Parallel Sessions

1. FINE1 session on "Noise"
Room George Stephenson

- 13:30-13:40: Technical assessment and integration of N&V tasks on system level (Gerrit Falk, Bombardier Transportation)
- 13:30-14:20: Traffic noise scenarios and baseline for evaluation and monitoring of noise effects in 324 innovations (Philipp Geiger, Deutsche Bahn, Rüdiger Seifburg, Deutsche Bahn)
- 14:30-14:30: Interior noise modelling (Torsten Kolha, Bombardier Transportation)

2. FINE1 & OPEUS joint session on "Energy"
Room Friedrich List

Chair: 2. Key results & recommendations 13:30-13:50

- 13:50-13:55: Shift2Rail Energy KPI results (Hans-Joachim Göttsch)
- 13:55-14:10: Energy Label & EN 50591 (Wolfgang Bombardier Transportation)
- 14:10-14:30: EU energy-efficiency policies (Michael Altmann, Alstom)
- 14:30-14:40: OPEUS Position Paper (Johannes Dübber, UTP)
- 14:40-15:00: Facilitated discussion, Q&A (15:00-15:10: Short break)

SPEAKERS

Harald Aschermann, University of Rostock

He received the doctoral degree in mechanical engineering from Leibniz University Hannover, Germany in 1994. After two years of working in research and development with a leading company in machine tools, where he designed sophisticated transfer systems, he joined the Institute of Materials, Control and Metrology, Faculty of Engineering and Computer Science, University of Roost. He received the Ph.D. degree with work on optimal trajectory planning and trajectory control of an overhead travelling crane in 2001 and, afterwards, he served as a Research Associate and lecturer in 2006 at this Institute.

Since 2006, he has been a Full Professor and the Head of the Chair of Mechatronics, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Marine Technology, University of Rostock, Germany.

William Bird, DG RTD Representative

Graduate of Oxford University, member of the UK Institution of Mechanical Engineers and the Institution of Logistics and Transport.

He spent the first 20 years of his career at British Rail, working in the Mechanical & Electrical Engineering Department on Rolling Stock, before becoming

For more info

Holke Brick for FI

Christine Hassou

Laurent Dauby, UTP

Heider Dittus, DLR

Jürgen Ernst, Deutsche Bahn AG

Dennis Faust, Bombardier Transportation

Rüdiger Seifburg, Deutsche Bahn AG

Philipp Geiger, Deutsche Bahn AG

Samuel Altmann, Alstom

Torsten Kolha, Bombardier Transportation

Tom Lennartz, SNCB

Tatjana Vlastakis, Capgemini

Miguel Morales-Guerra, Alstom

Divin An Nguyen, SAPT Batters

Roberto Palacin, Newcastle University

Lukas Probst, University of Rostock

Julian Sander, SNCB/UTP

Nasim Sanei, Alstom

Henry Vostler, Bombardier Transportation

7.2. List of attending companies

Organization	Which session are you planning to attend?
Akustikdoktorn Sweden	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Alstom	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Alstom	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Alstom	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Alstom	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
BELS-MIRALNIG.LTD	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Bombardier Transportation	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Bombardier Transportation	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Bombardier Transportation	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Bombardier Transportation	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
CAF	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
CALMA-TEC friendly noise company	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
CSTB	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
DB Systemtechnik GmbH	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
DB Systemtechnik GmbH	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Deutsche Bahn AG	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Deutsche Bahn AG	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Deutsche Bahn AG	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
DLR	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
DLR	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Eindhoven University of Technology	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
European Commission - DG RTD	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
KTH Royal Institute of Technology	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
LLC "AVP Technology"	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
London South Bank University	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Newcastle University	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Newcastle University	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SAFT	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SBB	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Shift2Rail JU	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Siemens Mobility	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Siemens Mobility	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy

Organization	Which session are you planning to attend?
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF - Innovation et Recherche	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
SNCF Mobilités	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF Mobilités CIM	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
SNCF Réseau	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Stadler	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Talgo	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Talgo	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Technical University of Berlin	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Thales	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
TNO	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
TNO	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Trafikverket	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
TU Dresden	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
UIC	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
UIC	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
UIC	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
UIC	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
UITP	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
UITP	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
UNIFE	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
UNIFE	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Universität Rostock	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
University of Birmingham	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
University of Rostock, Chair of Mechatronics	2) FINE 1 & OPEUS Joint Session on Energy
Vibratec SA	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise
Vibratec SA	1) FINE 1 Session on Noise

7.3. Copy of one email sent for reminder of conference

The image shows a screenshot of an email reminder for a conference. At the top, there are three logos: FINE1, Shift2Rail, and OPEUS_. Below the logos, the text reads: "LAST REMINDER", "FINE 1 & OPEUS Final Conference", "17 October 2019", "UIC, Paris, France", and "16 Rue Jean Rey, F-75015 Paris, France". A blue button with the text "Register" is centered below the text. Below the button, there is a paragraph of text: "This joint final event will be the opportunity to present the results achieved in the projects and to discuss how these results may improve the energy consumption of rail systems in the future and advance the state-of-the-art in noise modelling." This is followed by a bolded line: "Don't miss out on this important event and if haven't done so yet register by Tuesday, 15th October!". Below that is a link: "Click here to download the full agenda." Then another paragraph: "For additional information on the event, please contact FINE 1 coordinator Haike Brick at haike.brick@rail.bombardier.com or OPEUS dissemination coordinator Christine Hassoun at hassoun@uic.org." Finally, it says "Looking forward to seeing you in Paris!". At the bottom, there are two links: "unsubscribe from this list" and "update subscription preferences".